

Site: SPHINX Season GS 80

Area: NWa Square R19 Locus Number ① - ②

Progress of Excavation An area of removal of loose sand, limestone fragments was marked off at the upper NW corner of the "amphitheater" to clear the face of the upper ledge for a contact point between lower and upper rock units in Sphinx Area. Men cleared loose sand immediately on N side of Saite structure before tomb opening (N of Late Muddbrick enclosure wall). The lower bed of upper unit (II1) juts out to E. Abutting its vertical descent there was encountered a level of gravel w/ some granite frags, dolomite frag, sherds. This level (②) may be modern as frags were taken paper frags from it - but not certain.

Locus Description ① LOOSE DRIFT SAND, LIMESTONE FRAGS.
② LIMESTONE GRAVEL

Location in Square ② ABUTTING FACE

Under Locus ① SURFACE ② Over Locus _____
Locus Dimensions ① ②

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____